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Accounts of Adult English Language Learners in Their Classroom Communication: A Phenomenology

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Abstract

This qualitative study described the accounts of five (5) adults English language learners from Gani L. Abpi College Incorporated, Datu Piang, Maguindanao. The study is based on Cross's (1981), theory that adult learning characteristics have been primarily focused on understanding how adults learn. Thus, it was utilized the phenomenological research design described by Colaizzi's, (1978) seven steps strategy that provided a meticulous analysis of data. The transcription and translation, as well as classifying statements into themes, were employed with in-depth interview with the participants purposively chosen. The findings revealed that adult English language learners met different factors in learning English in the classroom communication. Agism, English language is interesting, anxiety affects English language learning, English language is not easy to learn were all highlighted as personal factors in learning the language. Teaching strategy and style matter, teachers' attitude affect learning, teacher-student age gap affects learning, and teachers' command of the English language is relevant were all identified as teacher factors. Peer factors entailed adopting to the group, peers encouragement is important, peer learning and guidance play a vital role and past experiences and misunderstanding affect learners. English as a factor for future endeavors, complexity of the subject matter, the learners' interest affect learning of the subject matter and the difficulty of the subject matter depends on the learners' perceptions highlighted as subject matter factors. Thus, the four factors, personal factors, peer factors, teacher factors, and subject matter factors influenced the accounts of Adult English language learners in their classroom communication resulted to challenges in learning second language in the classroom communication.

Keywords: *adults learners, english language learning, factors, phenomenology*

Introduction

Adults are performance-driven and they are constantly looking for ways to apply new knowledge. They are wary of new information and seek to put concepts to the test before adopting them. Adults are generally preoccupied with their desired objectives. If learning does not lead to desired outcomes, they become disengaged with it.

Adult learners, also known as overage students, are a broad collection of people aged 25 and above who come from a variety of educational and cultural backgrounds as well as adult responsibilities and work experiences. They do not usually enroll in higher education right after high school, as is the case with most people. They frequently return to school in order to maintain their competitiveness in the workplace or to prepare for a career transition. They frequently study part-time, taking one or two courses every semester while juggling work and family obligations (Board of Education for the Southern Region, 2015).

These Adult English Language Learners struggle to make expected progress in English as a second language (ESL) lessons, demonstrate success on evaluation measures, and keep their jobs. Learning problems may play a role in some of these difficulties. Learning impairments are disorders that cause difficulty in acquiring and using skills such as mathematical ability and social interaction, according to the Federal Interagency Committee on Learning Disabilities (Brown & Ganzglass, 1998).

The Philippines boasts one of the most extensive second-chance education systems in the world. It has 5.5 million adolescent and adult learners and is known as the Alternative Learning System or ALS. Adult learners pay a hefty price for education, especially if they have to quit their jobs to study. They have a wide range of academic backgrounds, talents, and learning motivation. (<http://www.deped.gov.ph>). Adult English language learners have been reported in the Bangsamoro Autonomous Region in Muslim Mindanao (BARMM), especially in Maguindanao Province. Despite their advanced age, some of these adult students continue to study. As a result, some people believe that these adult English language learners struggle to learn and communicate in English in the classroom.

Many educators have had to think about their performance and experiences in learning English in the classroom communication because of adult learners. While there have been a large number of studies conducted abroad, studies on adult English language learners in the Philippines are still lacking. There have been few local studies, but the most of them have concentrated on the level of awareness among teachers when it comes to teaching these types of students. Adult learners are under pressure since they are expected to have a higher level of English proficiency. In the worst-case scenario, when these adult English language learners make mistakes in the classroom, they may become a laughingstock to their young classmates. As a result, this research will aid Adult English language learners and teachers in better understanding the challenges and linguistic requirements of Adult English language learners. Furthermore, the findings of this study may serve as a catalyst for other researchers to conduct studies similar to the current topic.

Furthermore, the purpose of this study is to provide educators with information about these adult students' experiences so that they may develop effective ways and provide better assistance to adult learners. In this context, the researcher would like to conduct this study

that will investigate into this phenomenon of adult English language learners in classroom communication.

Research Questions

This study aimed to describe the experiences of adult English language learners at Gani L. Abpi College Incorporated, Buayan, Datu Piang, Maguindanao, Bangsamoro Autonomous Region in Muslim Mindanao (BARMM) during the school year 2021-2022. Specifically, it sought to answer the following research questions:

1. What are the experiences of adult English language learners in the classroom communication in terms of:
 - 1.1. personal factors;
 - 1.2. teacher factors;
 - 1.3. peer factors; and
 - 1.4. subject matter factors?
2. Based on the findings, what linguistic generalization can be made?

Methodology

Research Design

This is a phenomenological qualitative research study. It explained why five (5) adult English language learners were able to communicate in a classroom setting. This study examined adult learners' performance in the classroom when learning English, as well as their experiences in the classroom when using English as their primary language.

Qualitative research involves much smaller number of people and cases. Patton, (1990), as cited by Mohamad, (2022). Using a qualitative approach which primary purposes are to inquiry, extensive data collection, inductive and deductive data analysis, data presentation, researcher's reflexivity, and complex description and interpretation of the problem in the specific study (Crasswell and Poth, 2016). It entails taking an interpretative naturalistic approach to studying people or objects in order to clarify as well as uncover phenomena and meaning (Denzin & Lincoln, 2011), as cited by Crasswell and Poth (2016).

This study employs phenomenological research. This method is used to describe the data or analyze the results. Its goal is to convey the essence of an occurrence through into the eyes of those who have observed it. The goal of phenomenology would be to interpret the concept of experience at the time of both what and how it has been experienced. The data analysis process is rigorous and reliable, allowing it a qualitative approach that ensures the legitimacy and reliability of the results. It allows researchers to spot developing themes and their relationships. Researchers who adopt a descriptive phenomenological technique should think of it as a clear and logical manner to study an experience's essential structure Colaizzi, (1978).

Participants

The participants of this study were five (5) adult English language learners who are 25 years old and above from Gani L. Abpi College Incorporated for the School Year 2021-2022. The participants were chosen by the program adviser. The participants were chosen because they met the inclusion criteria set by the researcher which indicated that participant must be an English language learner, must be 25 year old and above and a bona fide student where the study is conducted.

To determine phenomenology, qualitative analysis often requires only a small sampling size of approximately three (3) to ten (10) cases, which was the basis for selecting the five (5) study participants. According to Crasswell's (1998) criterion, five to twenty-five individuals are needed for a qualitative phenomenological investigation, as cited in Samson (2017).

Instrument

In this study, the researcher conducted an in-depth interview. The instrument consists of open-ended questions intended to provoke information regarding the experiences and performances of adult English language learners. The researcher was guided through the process of conducting an in-depth interview using an interview procedure. It incorporated a discourse component in which the researcher and participants engaged in a guided dialogue during which the researcher allowed the participants to ask probing questions to learn more.

The study's objectives entailed determining adult English language learners' classroom communication experiences in terms of personal, peer, instructor, and subject matter aspects. The investigation's conclusions led to the development of linguistic generalization. Two (2) Masters Graduates in English and two (2) Doctors of Applied Linguistics made up this team of language professionals who assessed and validated the research questions and interview guide for the in-depth interview. These three professors are from Mindanao State University-Maguindanao Graduate Studies in Datu Odin Sinsuat, Maguindanao, and the last is the university's current Vice Chancellor for Academic Affairs. They have extensive research experience in addition to their impressive educational backgrounds and teaching experiences.

Following the validation of the instrument, an in-depth interview was arranged and conducted, each lasting 15-20 minutes. The researcher utilized a Vivo Y 11 to record audio and a portable digital camera to capture video and images during the interview.

Procedure

The following procedures were carefully followed during the conduct of the study.

The researcher did an in-depth interview in order to obtain significant data. The research procedures were considered when conducting the study. First and foremost, the researcher constructed a questionnaire based on the validated study questions. This questionnaire was thoroughly reviewed by language experts to ensure that it complied with the interview standards. Before administering the research instrument, the researcher got consent from the President of Gani L. Abpi College Incorporated, the College Directress of GLACI's College Department, and the study participants. The consent of the subjects is also required before the research can begin.

A schedule and place for the in-depth interview with the five (5) participants were set up with the help of the College Directress. The researcher was the one who asked the five (5) participants the interview questions during the in-depth interview. Hand washing, the use of alcohols and hand sanitizers, checking body temperature, wearing a facemask, and maintaining a 1-meter physical separation were all observed during the in-depth interview. The researcher also worked hard on the audio and video recording, transcription, and translation of the interview.

Data Analysis

This phenomenological study was conducted using Colaizzi's (1978) approach, which was discussed by Morrow, R., and Rodriguez, A. (1) familiarization, (2) identifying significant statements, (3) formulating meanings, (4) clustering themes, (5) developing an exhaustive description, (6) producing the fundamental structure, and (7) seeking verification on the fundamental structure, according to King (2015), Samson (2017), and Udat (2020). Mohamad, (2022), Delmundo et al., (2022), Zaniel, Mohamad & Parcon, (2023), Manakan, Untong, Mohamad & Sinsuat, (2023), Ugalingan, et al., (2023), Pulindao & Mohamad, (2023), Butukan, et al., (2024).

The researcher familiarized himself with the data by reading all of the participants' accounts numerous times and meticulously following these processes. The results of an in-depth interview were interpreted using thematic analysis. Finally, based on the information gathered, the researcher developed findings, conclusions, and recommendations

Ethical Considerations

The researcher followed the research methods established by Mindanao State University-Maguindanao Graduate Studies in this work. Ethical considerations in conducting for the consent of academic bodies to secure and protect personal identities from harm and risk were forcefully asserted (Denzin and Lincoln, 2003) as cited in Udat (2020). As a result, the researcher followed these ethical guidelines to the letter. The researcher established ethical standards by obtaining informed consent from the study participants and delivering transmittal documents such as letters of permission from the School President, the College Directress, and the participants for approval.

The data of the participants were kept confidential as part of the ethical consideration. Furthermore, research questions were crafted and designed with the diversity of each participant in mind, ensuring that no rights were violated and that no participants were offended, hurt, or insulted in any way during the study.

Credibility was established by gathering reliable and accurate data from the five (5) adult participants through in-depth interviews in which they openly revealed their thoughts and experiences with learning English in the classroom. During the in-depth interview, the participants described their experiences in terms of personal factor, peer factors, teacher factors, and subject matter factors in English language acquisition by answering guiding questions based on the study's research topics.

Setting the inclusion criteria in the selection of the five (5) adult participants, identifying the study's location in this context, Gani L. Abpi College Incorporated, Datu Piang, Maguindanao, and describing the accounts of adult English language learners in learning English language in the classroom communication were all used to achieve transferability.

The extensive descriptions and careful implementation of the study process and procedure ensured dependability, resulting in consistent findings that can be duplicated by other researchers. However, by carefully developing and applying study methodologies, the researcher guaranteed that the findings were taken into consideration and duplicated.

Finally, conformability measures the degree of fairness in the research study's conclusions. The researcher in this example ensured that bias did not affect the interpretation of the participants' responses to fit a particular narrative. The conclusions of the researcher were based on real data acquired from the research participants. The audit trail was created to emphasize each step of the data analysis in order to provide an explanation for the decisions made and to ensure that the research study's conclusions accurately reflect the replies of the participants.

Results and Discussion

This is a phenomenological study which employed Colaizzi's data analysis model to analyze the lived experiences of the adult English language learners in their classroom communication. The data were collected through participants' audio and video recordings during the in-depth interview. The data were carefully transcribed and translated in English. Further, the participants shared salient accounts on their experiences in learning English language in their classroom communication in terms of peer factors, personal factor, subject

matter factor and teacher factor. And based on the findings of the study, a linguistic generalization was made.

Different Factors Experienced by the Adult English Language Learners upon Learning English Language in the Classroom Communication

Through the process of identifying significant statements from each transcript of interviews to formulation of meanings and clustering of themes that establish the surface patterns, the themes were formulated. Four themes emerged to describe the experiences of adult English language learners in classroom communication. These identified themes are: Adult Language Learners in Learning English Language in terms of Personal Factors, Adult Language Learners in Learning English Language in terms of Teacher Factors, Adult Language Learners in Learning English Language in terms of Peer Factors, and Adult Language Learners in Learning English Language in terms of Subject Matter Factors.

Table 1. *Adult Language Learners in Learning English Language in terms of Personal Factors*

Code	Significant Statements	Formulated Meanings	Clustered Themes	Emergent Themes
(P1,A3)	“My age doesn’t affect my interest in learning English language.”	Age does not matter in English language learning	Age as Factor in Learning the Language	Age is not Important
(P5,A2)	“Age is not a hindrance to my learning.”			
(P2,A3)	“My age doesn’t bother me to learn English Language.”			
(P1,A4)	“I am interested and enjoy learning English Language...”	Arouses in learning English Language	Interest to learn English Language	English Language is Interesting
(P5,A3)	“I am interested in learning English language....”			
(P4,A3)	“I am interested in using English language....”			
(P2,A4)	“I have one hundred percent interest....”			
(P3,A2)	“I experienced anxiety when using it and getting it right.”	Language anxiety experienced in learning English language	Anxiety to learn the language	Anxiety affects English Language Learning
(P2,A2)	“Sressed pa ako sa spelling at meaning ng mga salita...”			
(P1,A4)	“It is hard to become comfortable in using English language...”	Discomfort in using English language	Hesitancy to learn and use the Language	English Language is not Easy to Learn
(P2,A5)	“I am not comfortable in using English language.”			
(P4,A4)	“I am not comfortable in using English language in the classroom communication.”			
(P5,A4)	“I am not comfortable in using English language because I am not too good in speaking English.”			

Language acquisition is one of main aspect before a person does communication both L1 and L2. The second language is considered more difficult to master than the first language because it is usually done as an adult and with a specific purpose. Khrasen (1982) explained language acquisition related to the first language, while language learning refer to second language, however the goal also acquisition. In acquisition or mastering the second language, can be influencing internal and external factors. a number of internal factor such as age, aptitude, anxiety, motivation, attitude, self esteem, cognitive style, specialization hemisphere, and learning strategies. The external factors include strategy learning, teaching context, social and culture.

Moreover, internal factor refers to personal factors to acquire second language. Each person has important role in the process of SLA. A person carries character which different ways and deal with situations in unique and personal style. According to Murray and Mount (1996), the extent of an individual’s achieved information depends on his/her individual personality.

In this study, internal factors or personal factors that encapsulated from the participants experiences are age is not important in learning the language, English language is interesting, anxiety affects English language learning, and English language is not easy to learn.

Age is not Important in Learning English

The effects of age on second language learning are not as straightforward as common belief or even some linguists would have us think. Scarcella et. al.,(1979) stated in their various reviews of age, arrive to general, if uncertain, solutions, as articulated by David Singleton: In naturalistic contexts, those whose experience to a second language begins in childhood in general outperform those whose exposure begins in adulthood, notwithstanding the latter's initial advantage. Cook (1986) focused on the research literature's methodological limitations, questioning the over-reliance on educated immigrants as subjects, English as a second language, Indo-European languages as the first language, the United States as the primary source of immigration, the limited aspects of language tested in the research, and the learners' date of arrival rather than their age of start. The benefits and drawbacks of age in the context of Second Language Acquisition study are yet unknown.

Certainly, finding an overall Critical Period effect with a specific cut-off age is difficult. Furthermore, age plays a role from conception to death. The difference between children and adults in terms of Second Language Acquisition is not the only factor to consider; Second Language Acquisition can also occur in old age (Clyne, 1985).

In this regards, the first personal factor identified in the transcripts was age as a factor in learning the language, as participants narrated:

“My age does not affect my interest in learning English language.” (P1, A3)

“Age is not a hindrance to my learning.” (P5, A2)

“My age does not bother me to learn English language.” (P2, A3)

The responses demonstrate adult English language accounts in terms of personal factors impacting language learning in age as a factor in language learning. This means that adult learners' age as a factor in learning English language is not an issue when it comes to learning the second language. Furthermore, it is noted in the comments above that the participants' age had no bearing on their desire to learn a second language.

According to Ekstrand (1976), He stated that with age, one's ability to learn a second language improves. Further, late beginners, according to Harley (1986), have a higher rate of acquisition. Therefore, we can get the point that older learners are efficient language learners or we can say that “the older the better.”

On the contrary, one of the participants expressed,

“Umm, my age affects my learning because as an adult learner, my memory to remember words or ideas doesn't stay for long term.” My age affects my learning because as an adult learner, my memory to remember words or ideas does not stay for long term. (P4, A5)

The aforementioned statement is a striking contrast to the responses that age has no bearing on adult learners' English language development. The participant stated that age has a significant impact on the learning of some adult learners. Furthermore, as an adult learner, the words and ideas are not retained for lengthy periods of time, that is why aging has a significant impact on adult learners' learning.

Adolescents and adults differ significantly from young learners. Older students are cognitively developed, which prevents them from learning language in a natural, or subconscious way. Formal settings with clear instructions and unambiguous rules benefit them (Hyland, 2019). With the exception of pronunciation, researchers indicate that older students surpass younger students in academic achievement (Spinner & Gass, 2019). Repetition and memorization aid adolescents, and they do poorly in public events. Adults are more organized, self-motivated, and accountable, making teaching easier (Ziglar & Ozfidan, 2016).

English Language is Interesting

A strong foundation for deeper learning is the development of interest (Hidi and Renninger, 2019). These views and their evolution are integrated into a four-phase model of interest development that has been identified: Specific situations elicit attention, which can then build over time and across situations to become more durable. The person's attention is drawn to the environment's traits (for example, novelty, ambiguity, and surprise). If duties appear relevant and engrossing, this situational interest can continue longer than a single setting (That is, if the student considers the task to be worthwhile or fun).

Early experiences of triggered and sustained situational attention can evolve into a growing individual interest, prompting the individual to seek out chances to actually engage with the object. Finally, this new individual interest can mature into a self-sustaining, well-developed interest (e.g., the student visits art museums and majors in art history). The idea is for individuals to deliberately seek for value for themselves. Indeed, self-generated utility-value interconnections are more powerful in encouraging interest and performance than externally provided utility-value information including when teachers directly tell learners that information is useful (Canning & Harackiewicz, 2015). Interest is a formidable stimulant which thus energizes learning and directs academic and professional paths (Renninger & Hidi, 2019).

As reflected in the experienced shared by adult language learners in learning English language on personal factors, the second identified factor is the interest to learn English language and as quoted by the following participants:

“I am interested and enjoy learning English language...” (P1, A4)

“I am really interested in learning English language even though I am not good in English language. (P5, A3)

The responses above represent the perspectives of adult English language learners in terms of interest in learning the language. One of the human characteristics that influence learning is a desire to learn a second language. This is because adult learners are more likely to engage in language acquisition when they are interested. When there is a strong desire to acquire a second language, there is a good probability of learning the target language as well. A person could not only commence learning but then also make it important by embracing an inner sense of curiosity.

In reality, this genuine desire and interest for adequate information as well as information by means of questioning thinking has aided

humans in making sense of the world, which has aided human intellect in many ways. This is especially relevant since recent experimental research in psychology and neuroscience have shown that experiencing states of curiosity promotes retention of information as well as acquisition among individual children and young adults (Oudeyer et al. 2016).

Participant 4 shared:

“I am interested in using English language especially when there is role playing”. (P4, A3)

It can be noted that participant’s interest in using English language is triggered when there is role playing in the classroom activities. Role play is a form of activity that is used in a range of communication learning methods. Numerous research findings throughout areas of study have characterized knowledge acquisition as such a methodology which it actively engages learners with their own learning experience, allowing teachers to act as guides and supporting opportunities for learners to grow (Ghilay & Ghilay, 2015; Graaf et al., 2005; Pekdoan & Kanak, 2016). Learners play an active role throughout their process of learning by using critical thinking to represent characters and make decisions about how to progress through the scenario.

Another participant narrated:

“I have one hundred percent interest because English language is essential nowadays...” (P2, A4)

In this response, participant shared his high interest in English language. English language plays an essential role in our lives as it helps in communication. It is the main language in studying any subject all over the world. English is the most widespread business language, the most popular entertainment in the world is in English, English is the most useful language for travel, English is the language of the online world, and English is the easiest language in the world to learn (Taylor, 2020). Thus, the participants' statement that English is important nowadays is supported by this article.

Anxiety Affects English Language Learning

Emotional responses are natural responses to upcoming, ongoing, and past events, and they are always present in academic settings (Mazer, 2017). Anxiety is the feeling of hopelessness and worry that is linked to a certain item. Lower student performance has been linked to higher anxiety in several studies (England, 2017). According to Begham (2016), learners absolutely detest trying new things whenever speaking English just because it allows them to feel anxious. Gopang et al., (2018) assessed Malaysian tertiary students' communication anxiety that concluded that anxiety used to have a detrimental effect on motivation.

In this study, participant 3 narrated:

“I experienced anxiety when using it [the English language] and getting it right.” (P3, A2)

The remark made by the participant above revealed that he experienced language anxiety in learning the language and using it correctly. Language anxiety has been observed to impede language learning, particularly in the development of the four skills, according to Dewey et al., (2018), who urge that efforts be made to identify areas of ESL students' concerns, calm them down, and research the roots of their fears. This may be due to the fact that acquisition would be both intellectual and subjective; therefore, successful learning can take place whenever English learners approached target language teaching with worry or trepidation. When something pertains to information exchange inside the target language, the social dimension of foreign language speaking anxiety can damage ESL learners' confidence and self-esteem.

Communication apprehension is a subjective characteristic in ESL/EFL circumstances, and it is described as a key component in individual differences in second language acquisition that teachers must consider. Yaman (2016) discovered that communication apprehension had a substantial impact on Speakers of other languages learners' academic achievement and proposed recommended teachers minimize the adverse impacts of anxiety in ESL courses.

Another participant also shared:

“Stressed pa ako sa spelling at meaning ng mga salita kasi may mga salitang hindi mo akalain na ganoon ang spelling at minsan may mga words na parehas ng spelling at meron din parehas ng bigkas peru magkaiba ng spelling. At kapag ginamit mo sa sentence may ibat-ibang meaning Nakaka-worry.” I got stressed in spelling and meaning because there are words which are the spelling is out of the pronunciation and there are words with the same pronunciation but not the same with spelling. And when you used it in the sentence there are different meanings. I got worried. (P2, A2)

The remarks made by the participants above revealed that adult English language narrative in terms of personal factors impacting language acquisition, with a focus on language anxiety. The rules to observe when using the target language make it harder for participants to learn the language. The participants were also perplexed and concerned since some of the words were difficult to spell and others were homonyms. Words' meanings change based on how they are used or where they are placed in a sentence.

On the other hand, process of learning could be encountered in communication, learning, thinking, or communicating, according to Sadiq et al., (2017), and that can adversely impact individuals' perspectives regarding communication skills. Furthermore, language anxiety has been identified as a significant element determines the performance or success of English learners

English Language is not Easy to Learn

The mechanisms of morphological and syntactic selections are obviously linked to hesitating phenomenon (Maclay and Osgood , 1959). In this study, one of the personal factors found in the transcripts of the interviews was the hesitation to learn and use the language. In fact, the participants shared that:

“Sir, uuuuumm, the truth is, it is hard to become comfortable in using English language...” Sir, the truth is, it is hard to become comfortable in using English language. (P1, A4)

“I am not comfortable in using English language.” (P2, A5)

“I am not comfortable in using English language in the classroom communication.” (P4, A4)

Speaking would be the second most useful of the language learning process (Raba, 2017). It can be gleaned that English language learning is difficult because of adult learners are hesitant to learn and use the language. This might be because the language is difficult and that difficulty results to discomfort in using the language. When adult learners felt discomfort in using the target language in the classroom communication, they become hesitant to learn and use the second language. They feel fearful to speak the language in front of the people because they lack confidence about their own competence in English. When individuals have chance to communicate, they may struggle to communicate effectively.

The effect of the very first language, a shortage of vocabulary, and indeed the family socio - economic level all impede English language learning, according to literature among Malaysian students (Misbah et al., 2017). In contrast, Psychological problems including such worry, nervousness, low confidence, and commitment, according to El-hadi et al., (2015) are indeed the major reasons for high school and higher level students' hesitation when speak in English..

Participant 4 added:

“Actually Sir, I... I am not comfortable in using English language because I am not too good in speaking English. Nabubulol ako minsan at minsan pa nga nauulit ang mga words ko kapag nagsasalita ako.” Actually Sir, I am not comfortable in using English language because I am not too good in speaking English. Sometimes I got stuttered and repeated words when I speak. (P5, A4)

The statement of the participant above implied that he had experienced hesitation in using the target language which resulted to stuttering and repetition of words when using language. Adults whose stammer have even more quantity and white matter coherence in dorsolateral prefrontal pathways, and enhanced significant factor interconnectivity is inversely connected overall stumbling frequency (Neef et al., 2018). Additionally, when contrasted to proficient counterparts, brain vibrations indicating periodic changes in neuronal responsiveness seem unnecessarily accentuated in individuals whom stuttering, exhibiting greater beta interruptions and synchronization throughout speaking formulation and execution (Mersov et al., 2018). Apprehensions are brief pauses that have been filled to the brim with something. Whenever people exhibit speaking maladaptive behavior in formulating phrases, they experience uncertainty. Clark and Fox Tree (2002) theory of hesitation constitute elements of a peripheral communication wherein the presenter is reflecting on competence.

Clark and Fox Tree believe that uncertainty follows the "phonology, prosody, syntax, semantics, and pragmatics of English words" in their detailed reasoning. It is frequently employed in the study of reluctance, particularly in pragmatics. It provides a thorough understanding of the significance, one of the most commonly utilized hesitations. Additional people must acquire not just the requisite language as well as the relevant speaking competence in ability to talk in just about any foreign tongue (Santos et al., 2016). We must improve our comprehension of linguistic knowledge up in a particular situation so that together we can comprehend whether as well as how to say with somebody, in which we are communicating, including what we have been attempting to speak over (Santos et al. 2016).

Table 2. *Adult Language Learners in Learning English Language in terms of Teacher Factors*

<i>Code</i>	<i>Significant Statements</i>	<i>Formulated Meanigs</i>	<i>Clustered Themes</i>	<i>Emergent Themes</i>
(P1,A5)	“Their teaching style was very effective.”	Effectiveness of teaching strategy and styles of the teachers	Teaching Strategy and Styles	Teaching Strategy and Styles Matter
(P3,A6)	“Their teaching styles are very effective but some are not.”			
(P4,A6)	“Teaching styles of my teachers are effective and some is... are not.”			
(P2,A6)	“The teaching style of my teachers is that more on students-centered...”	Teachers’ treatment towards adult learners	Attitude and command towards adult learners	Teachers’ Attitudes Affect Learning
(P5,A5)	“Um, I encountered a lot of teaching styles of our teachers. Ah one of those is the called facilitator, this one is the the opposite of lecturer....”			
(P4,A7)	“The teachers’ attitude and rules and regulation in teaching English language really affect my learning....”			

(P2,A7)	“Teachers’ attitudes really matters for the students learning....”			
(P5,A7)	“English language is always observed in the classroom communication....”			
(P1,A5)	“I am older than the other teachers, I am not comfortable because of it”	Discomfort in approaching teachers	Teacher-student Relation	Teacher-student Age Gap Affects Learning
(P4,A3)	“My age affects my relation to my teachers in the way that I felt shy on approaching them because they are younger than me.”			
(P5,A6)	“They treated as equally no discrimination in terms of age.”			
(P4,A8)	“Ang mga teachers ay fluent sa paggamit ng English language at nainspire nila ako dahil doon.”	Teachers mastery and fluency in using language	Teachers’ ability to use the language	Teachers’ Command of the English Language is relevant
(P1,A6)	“I started getting interested in learning the English language seeing my English subject teachers very fluent at using the language...”			
(P2 A7)	“When the teacher speaks English language kapag nakikipag usap sa amin or sa classroom interaction, natututo rin kami magsalita ng English dahil naa-adopt namin....”			

Every student learning method is normally handled in some kind of an information and training language that is appropriate for the reality of any community. The efficacy of knowledge and skill improvement is also determined by the quality of communication channels in the classroom. It is consequently essential that teachers have such a strong command of the pedagogical language in order to attain the intended educational objectives. Communication, regardless of whether spoken symbolic, remained among the most effective instrument for worldwide communication that allows a number of humans to know one another (Aminu et al., 2020).

There is really no specific teaching approach that matches all instructional situations. This same consciousness portion about becoming an older schoolteacher is an important factor in knowing who you really are and how connects to certain other aspects of teaching and learning, including the development, organization, and facilitating procedures. The competence in becoming an autonomous learner inside a range of fields is aided by establishing steady and meaningful personality. As a result, schools and teachers included the development of high - quality personality in their students' as a whole educational objectives. Whereas personality, self-control, and self-expression are primarily developed by exposure towards the modeling of these kinds of behaviors in the surroundings, this alone will not offer educators with just an organized strategy on a regular basis (Cadima et al., 2015).

Teaching Strategy and Styles Matter

Finding appropriate instructional approaches and procedures that could also significantly improve learning activities to increase students' educational attainment is among the difficulties for educators. A competent teacher should modify his or her conduct in developing the skills and personality that will help them achieve their goals for themselves rather than the community. Whenever different teachers' instructional strategies and students' different learning are taken into account, it can help develop pupils with sufficient information and abilities to help them achieve good academic results. Consequently, the purpose of this study sought to see if the differentiated instruction of the teachers differed considerably first from learning processes of the pupils.

Each instructor has a different teaching style, as do the learning styles of their learners, which might affect their work achievement. Hearing, expressing, interpreting, and composing are the four skills that must be taught in English. Conversation in the second or third language / foreign tongue has recently become a more important part of communication in everyday life. Interpersonal language is a difficult task (Gilakjani cited in Leong & Ahmadi, 2017). Instructional strategy refers to the technique that teachers receive when educating students. Teaching methods differ depending upon the age. Hardly any of the methods are optimal. This method made it easier for the teacher to distribute the content to the students. These tactics may benefit the instructor while students are more engaged and can discuss their ideas with their peers (Sarjan, 2017).

A teaching strategy is a method or style of doing, producing, or performing anything. Several educational strategies as well as approaches are extremely beneficial to adult English language learners. As little more than a consequence, whenever developing plans courses, make sure to keep mature students in consideration. Ouyang and Scharber (2017) investigated the impact of instructional methods on student connectedness and performance over the academic period. The findings indicated that throughout the formative days of academics, instructors experienced a larger necessity engagement & contact, which evolved towards a more inactive curriculum implementation process.

Throughout the languages teaching and learning activities, both instructor's technique and demeanor became critical. Learning a new language seems to have a good probability of success if indeed the training process is suitable as well as the role of the teacher or

methodology is suited for the kind of students. In essence, student-teacher contact fosters a feeling of connectedness and coherence that promotes learning participation. Students are found to place a higher value on teacher-student relationships, which would be a proven measure of student learning satisfaction and retention (Lee & Bonk, 2016; Luo, Zhang, & Qi, 2017).

In this study, teaching strategy and style were reflected in the transcripts of interviews. In fact, participants narrated that:

“Their teaching style was very effective.” (P1, A5)

“Their teaching styles are very effective but some are not.” (P3, A6)

“Teaching styles of my teachers are effective and some is... are not.” Teaching styles of my teachers are sometimes effective and sometimes not. (P4, A6)

The responses above revealed that the adult English language learners had experienced effective and ineffective teaching strategies and styles of the teachers. This means that the adult English language learners have different learning styles that the teachers should consider when teaching the second language. Effective teaching requires flexibility, creativity, and responsibility in order to provide an instructional environment able to respond to the learner's individual needs.

According to Fleming (2017), neither any particular teaching style is effective for any and all pupils. As a result, teachers could perhaps implement a variety of instructional methodologies to satisfy multiple learning styles. Varied tactics provide contradictory conclusions, therefore determining whichever instructional approach should utilize among the many options can be useful to teachers. Despite the reality that both methods and techniques were used efficiently, methodological distinctiveness often does not guarantee student outcomes since not all students are taught in the very same manner (D'Amore & Sbaragli, 2011; Weber et al., 2020).

Moreover, participants 2 and 5 stated the strategies that the teachers employed in the classroom. These are reflected in the following lines:

“The teaching style of my teachers is that more on students-centered which is every student has their own assigned topic to present in the class, hinhayaan nila ang mga students to find solution on how they present their assigned topic. That teaching style is very good to us because it gives us an opportunity to practice our speaking skills in front of other students.” The teaching style of my teachers is that more on student-centered which is every student has his own assigned topic to present in the class. They let their students to find solution on how they present their assigned topic. That teaching style is very good to us because it gives us an opportunity to practice our speaking skills in front of other students. (P2, A6)

“Um, I encountered a lot of teaching styles of our teachers. Ah one of that is the called facilitator, this one is the the opposite of lecturer. They they allow us to express our thoughts in English language. Ah most of the time nagreport kami at natututo sa English language.” I encountered a lot of teaching styles of our teachers. One of those is the so called facilitator, that one is the opposite of lecturer. They allow us to express our thoughts in English language. Most of the time we do reporting and from that we are learning English language. (P5, A5)

Participants' statements above figured the teachers' teaching strategies in teaching second language. Participants 2 and 5 shared that one of the strategies used by the teachers is based on the student-centered approach. The responses above implied that adult learners had experienced learning more effectively when they personally experienced certain things like reporting topics in front of the class and used the English language in the classroom communication. This strategy gave opportunity to the students to explore while learning the target outcome while teachers act as facilitators in the learning process.

The learner-centered strategy used in this education - learning experience was largely influenced by andragogy, an adult literacy philosophy. Andragogy, according to Knowles (1978), is based on progressive theories of learning, with learning centered on the individuals and personality.

Moreover, student-centered learning is considered more effective because of sharing of communication mostly from presenter to the learners is indeed not centralized (Greitzer, 2002). Furthermore, rather than relying on the traditional lecture style, the usage of activities engaging and student-centered approaches like instructional strategies should be encouraged for higher academic achievement. LCD technology has progressed.

Lee and Hannafin (2016), for example, propose a theoretical design approach for LCD use. "Own it, learn it, and share it," they say. Their objective was to improve a comprehensive foundation for the use of LCD in real-world learning environments. They argue that their own methodology is founded on the necessity for schools to participate responsibly for learning organization in order to ensure learning experience and to study "independent using higher cognitive, methodological, theoretical, and strategy structuring; and have results that are targeted at authentic listeners" (Lee & Hannafin, 2016).

Teachers' Attitudes Affect Learning

Among the most important things impacting student achievement is teacher attitude. Students' performance might be influenced by teachers' attitudes and commands towards them. Every day, teachers issue commands to their students. Heterogeneous instructor aspirations therefore, throughout effect, students' academic routes have already been linked to teachers' views about their students.

Even though they engage with learners in the class, issue marks, and recommend kids to other school - based educational, teachers have a significant impact on their students' academic progress. Emotional responses (affective), perceptions, beliefs (cognitive), and behaviors make up perspectives (behavioural). Cooperation is bringing everything together thoughts and experience of people from various professional groups in achieving a shared goal (Igbo & Imo, 2017).

In this study, attitude and command towards adult learners were reflected in the transcripts of interviews. In fact, participants narrated that:

“The teachers’ attitude and rules and regulation in teaching English language really affects my my learning in classroom communication. The... the command of my teachers in using language affects my learning English language in the classroom.” The teachers’ attitude and rules and regulations in teaching English language really affect my learning in classroom communication. The command of teachers in using the language affects my learning English language in the classroom. (P4, A7).

Participant 4 stated that teachers’ attitude and command had affected adult learners in learning English language in classroom communication. The statement also implied that teachers’ attitude played important part in learning the target language. Teachers with positive views regarding a text, its communicators, and associated culture are much more effective in training classrooms than someone with poor feelings (Alptekin, 1984).

Participant 2 stated that:

“Teachers’ attitudes really matters for the students learning. The teacher helps to motivate and encourage students to learn. They are strict in using English language especially kapag nasa classroom na. And they treated as equal no discrimination in terms of age.” Teachers’ attitudes really matter for the students learning. The teacher helps to motivate and encourage students to learn. They are strict in using English language especially in the classroom. (P2,A7)

Participant 2 shared that teacher’s attitude matters in English language learning. As stated by the participant, positive attitude of the teachers can motivate and encourage students to learn the target language. In the disciplines of student learning and academic efficiency, teacher actions have received much interest (Kyriakides et al., 2020).

Any challenging activity's accomplishment is largely determined by motivation. It is commonly recognized that someone whose motivation determines their performance in an endeavor. It is indeed easy for people to say that along with the correct motivation, a student could very well succeed in a second or third language (Alizadeh 2016). A great teacher is one who can maintain strict influence over teaching and learning operations (Sun et al., 2018).

Participant 5 also reinforced that:

“English language is always observed in the classroom communication. May mga minus points talaga pag gumamit ng vernacular language sa classroom.” English language is always observed in the classroom communication. There are minus points when students used vernacular language in the classroom. (P5, A7)

Participant statement above implied that teacher’s command to employ certain rule in learning English language like plus and minus points might affect adult English language learning. Teacher control inside the school requires permission, considering anyone who is in a position of responsibility requires power to complete their tasks. Constitutional, motivational, specialization, references, and disciplinary powers are among the five types of authority identified (Esmaeili et al., 2015). By leveraging authoritative instruments, teachers can create an acceptable educational environment for kids in the classroom.

Teacher-student Age Gap Affects Learning

The teacher-student relationship can influence adult English language learning. In teaching-learning process, teachers and students have to be good partners. However, on the adult English language learning in the classroom communication, there should be a strong teacher-student relation so that learning the target language can be learned easier. The teacher-student interaction has really been recognized as a critical factor in enhancing student students’ academic performance. Teachers play an important role in instruction by assisting students in achieving their objectives. Cook et al. (2018) discovered that even some students who spent sufficient time with their professors during the week. As according Wu and Hughes (2015), the teacher-student interaction deteriorates as kids progress from early to late primary school. As students grow past elementary school and into high school, teachers' secure attachment may become more crucial.

As a matter of fact, participants revealed that:

“I am older than the other teachers, I am not comfortable because of it”. (P4, A8)

“Honestly Sir, my age affects my relation to my teachers in the way that I felt shy on approaching them because they are younger than me.” (P1, A6)

According to the above comments, Participants 4 and 1 reported that their teacher-student relationship has been impacted because they are hesitant to contact their teachers because they are older than their teachers. Participants also stated that they are uncomfortable in

learning English because of their age, which has a negative impact on their relationships with their professors. Students create favorable positive relationships with teachers whenever teachers and students exchange respect (Kranee et al. 2017). Teachers who encourage children to learn can have a favorable impact on their long-term achievement (Sinelnikov et al., 2016).

Participant 2 also narrated that:

“They treated us equally no discrimination in terms of age.” (P2 A7)

The statement implied that the adult English language learners had experienced the same treatment and engagement with the younger learners from their teacher in learning English language in the classroom communication. Student involvement is viewed as component of a bigger theory of motivation, with the classroom experience rebounding on how individuals perceive themselves (Fredricks et al., 2019). Despite the fact that commitment and lack of engagement are linked categories, assessing them independently could provide more detailed understanding of the phenomenon, as disengaged catches features that involvement ought to (Jang et al., 2016; Bergdahl et al., 2020). Furthermore, the majority of studies on student involvement and disengagement (O'Donnell and Reschly, 2020) have focused on kids with normal development (TD).

Teachers' Command of the English Language is Relevant

Throughout non-native English-speaking countries, any use of English language primary means of instruction (EMI) is becoming more frequent (Macaro et al., 2018). The approach of just using English to teach academic courses in countries where English is not the majority's first language (L1) is known as English as a means of instruction. The limited English level of teachers who use English is primary vehicle of teaching has been reported in several cultural situations (Bradford, 2016).

It is possible that EMI teachers' language difficulties contribute to their poor academic performance in the classroom (Wen et al., 2018; Pun and Thomas, 2020). Teachers' skill to use the language is also a factor in adult English language learning, according to the participants. According to Freeman (2017), the multi-dimensions of EMI teachers' teaching are linked to their classroom linguistic competence. The EMI context's hazy definition of "language competency" necessitates a better appreciation of the forms of competence essential for adequate instruction by EMI teachers (Macaro et al., 2021).

According to those participants who took part:

“Ang mga teachers ay fluent sa paggamit ng English language at nainspire nila ako dahil doon.” The teachers are fluent in using English language and they made me inspired because of that. (P1, A5)

“I started getting interested in learning the English language seeing my English subject teachers very fluent at using the language...” (P4, A3)

The aforementioned assertions implied that a teacher's ability to communicate in a foreign language can motivate adult learners to learn a second language. When the teacher is fluent in the target language, the students may be motivated to learn and utilize English in order to become fluent in it as well. Students' academic achievement and their overall development of communication skills tend to suffer when teachers do not master the language of instruction. Teachers extrinsically motivate the students to learn English language.

Motivation is a complicated social invention that really has unexplained reasons those attempting to comprehend and describe it (Anjomshoa and Sadighi, 2015). Mulvahill (2018) discusses intrinsic motivation as little more than a means of pleasure development and motivation because teachers are unable to modify students' mindsets. Alternatively, teachers can promote and encourage kids to learn.

Another participant shared that:

“When the teacher speak English language kapag nakikipag usap sa amin or sa classroom interaction, natututo rin kami magsalita ng English dahil naa-adopt namin. And that's one of the things na natututo kami sa English language because we can adopt that.” When the teacher speaks English language when communicating with us or in classroom interactions, we also learn to speak English because we eventually adopt it. And that is one of the things that we learn English language because we can adopt that. (P5, A6)

Participant 5 narrated that one factor of learning English language is when the teacher is using English language in the classroom communication. If the teacher used the language in the classroom, they eventually adopt it and used it also in their classroom communication. Communication is the real nature of students and teachers' condition in the classroom for developing communicative competence. This indicates that teachers help students to develop their interaction skills and practice English in the classroom.

Moreover, communication is the foundation of L2 learning, according to Brown (2015), wherein the individuals are committed including both improving their individual language competence and culturally creating actual personalities with teamwork and bargaining. Communication in classroom contexts has aimed to show that student individuals can learn despite constantly comparing the language being delivered to the students' first language.

Macaro et al., (2016) stated that building on previous research on the function of interaction in SLA, identified considerable learner exchanges as just a fundamental of stronger understanding during second language acquisition in language classes. Furthermore, it is

hypothesized that learners will not only acquire more language through participating in interactions but instead of listening to monologues from teachers (Gass, 2018)

Table 3. *Adult Language Learners in Learning English Language in terms of Peer Factors*

Code	Significant Statements	Formulated Meanings	Clustered Themes	Emergent Themes
(P4, A9)	“I am not part of the group”	Difficulty in adjusting to be part of young learners	Self-belongingness	Adopting to the group
(P2, A9)	“There are some points na ang mindset ko is not the same with them as well as my actions...”			
(P1, A8)	“I can’t understand them especially their interest”	Younger learners motivation in English language learning	Peers as motivators	Peers Encouragement is Important
(P1, A10)	“They motivated me to learn...”			
(P2, A11)	“They always encourage me...”			
(P3, A7)	“They are cheering me up to learn...”			
(P4, A10)	“They help and motivate me...”	Younger learners act as tutor to adult learners	Student to Student Learning	Peer Learning and Guidance Play a Vital Role
(P5, A10)	“They motivate me...”			
(P2, A10)	“They keep on asking me na gawin ang mga bagay na katulad mg ginagawa nila...”			
(P1, A9)	“They are guiding me on some parts that I didn’t experience in the past.”			
(P2, A15)	“I am always asking my classmates to explain to me the subject matter.”			
(P5, A9)	““they always one call away para tulungan ako...”	Miscommunication among adult learners and younger learners	Misunderstanding among peers	Past Experiences and Misunderstanding Affect the Learners
(P1, A2)	“My past experiences during my high school days was my classmates laugh at me...”			
(P2, A5)	“I am not confident in using English language because I am afraid...”			
(P5, A2)	“I am shy in using English because I am afraid of being judged by the young learners...”			

Adopting to the group, peers encouragement is important, peer learning and guidance play a vital role, and past experiences and misunderstanding affect learners are the emergent themes emerged as the overarching topic from the participants' shared experiences in English language acquisition in terms of Peer Factors. Adult English language learners learned particular things when there is a supporting system from their peers. Students' peer relationships can have an important role in their school adjustment and motivation. Peer engagement in the classroom setting is a naturally produced situation wherein the children acquire information and abilities, according to developmental theory and research (Coplan & Arbeau, 2009; Singer & Golinkoff, 1968).

Adopting to the Group

The strength of your connection and learning will be boosted if you are in a group of people of your age. Belonging is a major factor that contributes positively to an individual's psychological development. Number of studies have shown the relevance of consciousness and its intertwined link with a feeling of connection (Arslan, 2021).

According to the participants, self-belonging is also a component in learning English as a second language. They proved it with the lines below:

“I feel in myself that I am not part of the group.” (P4, A9)

“There are some points na ang mindset ko is not the same with them as well as my actions...” There are some points that my mindset is different with them as well as my actions.... (P2, A9)

“I cannot understand them especially their interest” (P1, A8)

Adopting to the group is one of the peer factors that influences adult English language acquisition, according to the participants'

statements, when learners feel that they are not a part of the group, their second-language acquisition suffers. Adult learners also noted that young learners' mindsets and actions differed from their own. Adult learners were led to believe that they were not a member of the group of youthful students as a result of this. Adult learners also struggled to understand the younger learners' interests. As a result, adult students experienced as if they were not actually a part of this group among students. Feelings about school, experiences, including connections among classmates and teachers are all examples of this requirement (Allen et al., 2018).

Peers Encouragement is Important

Student perceived support from their peer can result to student motivation in their academic performance. The adult English language learners stated that these young peers also motivate them regardless of the age that they have. Younger learners motivate adult learners to engage in the classroom activities. The rising impact of peer relationships connectedness on encouragement throughout early teenage years is rarely validated with the experimental research. The majority of the studies included several groups of people or look into periods of development like childhood and teenage years (Wentzel et al., 2020). Motivation, on the other hand, is indeed a multidimensional idea and component that is cognitive, conative, and emotive in character (Gardner, 1985). A student with a high level of motivation in the learning experience is engaged in the lesson, prepares for class, asks questions, participates in conversations, concentrates on the areas he or she needs to be taught, never stops trying, and is tenacious and interested in learning (Zambas, 2019).

According to the narrated experiences of the participants:

"They motivated me to learn despite of being an adult learner and I.....I realized that it's not too late for me to continue my studies." They motivated me to learn despite of being adult learner and I realized that it is not too late for me to continue my studies. (P1, A10)

"They always encourage me to do more to have a better result in my task." (P2,A11)

Other participants supported it:

"They are cheering me up to learn as an adult learner." (P3, A7)

"They help and motivate me to gain more knowledge and they always show appreciation in in my progress." They help me and motivate me to gain more knowledge and they always show appreciation on my progress. (P4, A10)

"Sir, Umm, they motivate me through their actions and from being interested in learning." Sir, they motivate me through their actions and for being interested in learning. (P5, A10)

Adult English language learners in the classroom showed high peer motivation for learning a second language, according to the comments above. The inspiration supplied by young students was extremely beneficial to adult learners. Extrinsic motivation occurs when adult learners are motivated by their younger students, which leads them to believe that learning is a meaningful process that can be learned if one is motivated. Furthermore, peer groups with strong ties would provide a greater sympathetic least competitive environment (Mundt et al., 2017).

Peer Learning and Guidance Play a Vital Role

Peer learning is not a single, undifferentiated educational strategy. It encompasses a broad sweep of activities. Peer-learning programs are now available on every corner and are beneficial to the students of many cultures. It is amongst the most important aspects of university teaching and learning, including one of the "the much more cost-effective learning methodologies" (Sneddon, 2015). The relevance of social connection in learning is stated by Vygotsky (1978). He then linked social constructivism, a theory that emphasizes the importance of social contact in peer learning. Peer learning promotes student engagement, reflection, and critical analysis through self- and peer assessment as they work through a sequence of "constructivist learning" active learning that assist them progress through the stages of peer learning.

In this study, adult English language learners also narrated their experiences on peer learning in their learning the second language as the participants emphasized the following:

"They keep on asking me na gawin ang mga bagay na katulad ng ginagawa nila para matulungan ako sa English language. Ah, they always support me as their adult classmate by means of sharing their ideas and encouraging me na magparticipate sa group works." They keep on asking me to do those things that they are doing so that they can help me to learn English language. They always support me as their adult classmate by means of sharing their ideas and encouraging me (P2, A10)

"They are guiding me on some parts that I didn't experience in the past." They are guiding me in some parts that I did not experience in the past. (P1, A9)

The statements of the participants above implied that younger learners and adult learners also had peer learning experiences. Younger learners shared ideas and encouraged adult learners to learn English language in the classroom communication. These younger learners are also guiding the adult learners in some parts that these adult learners did not encountered from their past experiences. The statements of the participants also suggested that learning second language became easy when there is peer learning. Collaborative learning as well as participating in peer-assisted learning teaches students how to cooperate and exchange ideas while also teaching them how to

live comfortably functioning together (Tus, 2020).

Participant 2 narrated that:

“I am always asking my classmates to explain to me the subject matter. They explain the subject matter for many times and that’s the way I learned the subject matter easily.” (P2, A15)

Participant 2 narrated that she used to ask her younger classmates to explain the topics. Younger learners helped adult learners by explaining the topics so that adult learners can understand it clearly. The participant also shared that she can easily understand the topic when younger classmates explain it to her. This implied that peer learning is might be an effective strategy to learn English language in the classroom communication. Peer learning improves academic achievement significantly (Yu et al., 2019). Furthermore, graduate student peer learning allows for skill improvement and social engagement from outside the supervisor-student connection (Cusick et al., 2015). According to Chilvers (2016), peer supported studying is one of the most effective ways for overseas students to acclimate to academic cultures in higher education.

Participant 5 also recounted that:

“Pag may mga salita ako na hindi maintindihan, they always one call away para tulungan ako. Minsan naghahanap pa sila ng way to help me in my reporting. And that’s the best thing to have these young learners. Tinutulungan talaga akong matuto sa English language.” Sometime when there is certain word which I do not understand, they are always one call away to help me. Sometime they always find ways to help me on my reports. And that is the best thing to have these young learners. They really help me to learn English language. (P5, A9)

According to the participant, the best thing about having these young learners is that they actually assist these adult learners in learning English through peer learning. Adult learners eventually learned things by themselves through peer learning. According to Andrianoff (2016), peer learning could indeed encourage students to develop self-directed academic skills, enhanced creativity, and problem-solving skills, as well as information exchange, emotional and social, and team - working, peer evaluation and essential forethought, and a profound conceptual understanding and skills.

Past Experiences and Misunderstanding Affect the Learners

Language serves as a means of communication between members of community (Pardede 2019). Language is utilized as a tool of information exchange, as according Herman (2017). Through communication, we may communicate with our acquaintances convey our thoughts, and sentiments. Miscommunication occurs in all forms of communication. Adult learners have many different perspectives concerning peer factors in English language development. Peer misunderstanding was a problem for numerous adult students. Misunderstandings can stymie adult learners' attempts to learn a second language. According to Neslon et al., (2002), misunderstanding occurs when a listener interprets an utterance's purpose as if it were something except what the speaker intended.

In fact, some of the participants claimed that:

“My past experiences during my high school days was my classmates laugh at me because of, uuuuuuummm, pronouncing an English words properly. They called me “maarte.” My experiences during my high school days were my classmates laugh at me because of pronouncing English words properly. They called me “maarte.” (P1, A2)

Participant 1 narrated that she had experienced to be called “maarte” by the younger learner because of pronouncing English word properly. She shared that younger learners also laughed at her and misunderstood her because of the way she used to pronounce words when using it in the classroom communication. The study about speakers meaning is called pragmatic. Mono (2018) stated that pragmatics is a branch of linguistics that focuses on the relationship underlying language and circumstance. According to Supriyadi (2020), the speaker utilizes a means-end analysis approach whereas the speech partner uses pragmatic assessment techniques to understand speech occurrences.

Other participants narrated that:

“I am not confident in using English language because I am afraid. I am afraid to be, to be judged by the young learners.” (P2, A5)

“I am shy in using English because I am afraid of being judged by the young learners...” (P5, A2)

The participants' statements revealed that when learners are misunderstood as a result of attempting to use a particular language, they may feel uncertainty to use the language because of the fear of their peers' judgments and misunderstandings. This result to adult student’s loses of his self-confidence. Individuals with a personality problem, on the other hand, feel that their talents are unchangeable irrespective whether previous efforts or experiences, and view performance problems as either opportunities to affirm their capabilities or challenges to prevent looking inept toward others (Papi et al. 2019). These students create performance targets and are concerned about how others will judge them.

According to Rubio-Alcala (2017), low levels of self has a significant influence on global language learning because of the interactions between both the learners and indeed the significant obstacle of learning other languages, which makes people feel unwilling to actually

"be themselves" while knowing the language. Furthermore, "learners experience severe uncertainties, nervousness, dread, and social stratification" as a result of failing to meet the teachers' and other students' expectations in class.

Table 4. *Adult Language Learners in Learning English Language in terms of Subject Matter Factors*

<i>Code</i>	<i>Significant Statements</i>	<i>Formulated Meanings</i>	<i>Clustered Themes</i>	<i>Emergent Themes</i>
(P2,A17)	"English language will be useful for me someday especially when looking for a job."	Language as a get way to a good future	Importance of English	English as Factor in Future Endeavors
(P4,A12)	"I know this is useful to me."	Difficulty in identifying and using words in properly and correctly	Word Recognition and Correct Usage	Complexity of the Subject Matter
(P3, A4)	"There are so many words with almost the same meaning making it difficult			
(P4,A11)	"The rules and structuring sentences and constructing ideas to make sentences in English language is difficult."			
(P2,A14)	"When it comes to grammar I am struggling to get the correct arrangement of the sentences	Adult learners interest in learning the subject matter	Interest and Willingness	The Learners' Interest Affect Learning of the Subject Matter
(P1,A12)	"I am so much interested to this subject!"			
(P2,A17)	"I am willing to learn English language..."			
(P3, A8)	"I am already gaining interest on it, and I am and will be willing to learn English even it requires more time	Unfamiliar words and synonymous words are difficult to identify	Challenges and Difficulties in Learning the Subject	The Difficulty of the Subject Matter Depends on the Learners Perceptions
(P1,A11)	"The subject matter is difficult because of not continuing my studies for almost 12 years..."			
(P2, A2)	"I can't easily catch up those words that are new to me. I did a lot of efforts to improve my fluency."			
(P5,A11)	"The subject matter is is difficult to me, ummm, because I am a slow-learner.	Unfamiliar words and synonymous words are difficult to identify	Challenges and Difficulties in Learning the Subject	The Difficulty of the Subject Matter Depends on the Learners Perceptions
(P4,A11)	"At my age, my experiences of learning the English language was challenging...."			

Subject Matter as a factor on Adult English language learning had become a crucial part in learning second language. This is because some adult learners had experienced how difficult the subject matter is, and some had experienced that the subject matter is interesting. Based on the shared experiences of the adult English language, there are factors on subject matter which included English as factor for future endeavors, complexity of the subject matter, the learners' interest affect learning of the subject matter, the difficulty of the subject matter depend on the learners' perceptions.

English as Factor for Future Endeavors

The first identified experiences of the adult English language in subject matter factors was the English as factor for future endeavors. English language is important because it is a way to understand people. Kim (2020) noted that learning culture is needed to facilitate the process of learning English for students and to increase student motivation in learning language.

In fact, the participants emphasized the following:

"English language will be useful for me someday especially when looking for a job." (P2, A17)

"I know this is useful to me" (P4, A12)

Adult English language learners recognized the importance and use of English, as seen by their response. When a person is proficient in the English language, there are a plethora of chances available to him. Some job applications demand English as a medium of communication, and if you are proficient in a second language, you will have an advantage over the competition. That is how important English seems to be. According Reddy (2016), English is the dominant language of business, and knowing English seems to be becoming a requirement for people who want to work in a highly skilled workforce.

Further, research from around has shown that cross-border business communication is frequently conducted in English. Learning English can truly transform your life. Learning English is essential because it helps people to share information effectively with other people from all over the world. The fact that English has become a world language is undeniable (Nishanthi, 2018).

Complexity of the Subject Matter

The second identified experiences of the adult learners on the subject factors was complexity of the subject matter. As quoted by the participants:

“There are so many words with almost the same meaning making it difficult. It is difficult to decide which word to use...” (P3, A4)

“The rules and structuring sentences and constructing ideas to make sentences in English language is difficult” (P4, A11)

“When it comes to grammar I am struggling to get the correct arrangement of the sentences...” (P2, A14)

Adult English language learners experienced difficulty in terms of semantics, notably in word recognition and correct usage, as evidenced by the responses of the participants. One of the difficulties among linguistic components, according to participants, is synonyms. Participants have a limited vocabulary or are unable to recognize terms with similar meanings, making learning a second language challenging. Richards and Renandy (2002) as cited in Udat (2020), mentioned that vocabulary is a core component of language proficiency and provides much basis for how learners speak, listen, read, and write.

Furthermore, participants stated that they have difficulty in organizing sentences or with language in general. Grammar was extremely important in the use of language. When grammar is poor, a statement might become nonsensical, and the message can get muddled. When studying English as a foreign language, grammar is crucial. Grammar aids student teachers in constructing English sentences in order to communicate with others. Other language skills such as listening, speaking, reading, and writing are linked to grammar. A thorough working grasp of grammar is required, as is the art of employing rhetoric to arrange words, phrases, sentences, and paragraphs in order to capture the attention of the reader (Muhsin et al., 2018).

The Learners' Interest Affect Learning of the Subject Matter

Another Subject matter factor that reflected on the experiences of Adult English language learners is the learners' interest affects learning of the subject matter. The following are the participants' statements:

“I am so much interested to this subject!” (P1, A12)

“I am willing to learn English language...” (P2, A17)

“I am already gaining interest on it, and I am and will be willing to learn English even it requires more time.” (P3, A8)

The statements above demonstrate adult English language learners' interest in and willingness to learn about the subject. Adult learners' interest piques their interest in learning a second language, whereas willingness is their decision to learn anything without reservation. Adult learners, according to the statement above, showcase interest and willingness to learn the academic content. They show a high level of enthusiasm in studying English because of their drive and readiness to learn. The importance of interest in learning has long been recognized. Interest is defined in the field of educational psychology as an interaction between a person and an object (i.e., a specific domain to learn) together within environment (Boekaerts & Boscolo, 2002).

Moreover, according to IDC theory, around 10 percent of total of the diversity in learning can indeed be addressed by factors associated to interest, according to a meta-review of studies that have assessed affects of interest on learning (Wong et al., 2020). As a result, encouraging student interest in the outcome to be learned could make learning easier.

Difficulty of the Subject Matter Depends on the Learners' Perception

Adult English language learner experienced difficulties in learning the Subject Matter. Participants shared difficulties that they had experienced in learning the subject matter. The following statements show the challenges and difficulties in the subject matter:

“The subject matter is difficult because of not continuing my studies for almost 12 years. Some of the topics was already tackled in the past and I already forgot it. The subject is difficult to me because I didn't undergone Senior High School curriculum.” The subject matter is difficult because of not continuing my studies for almost 12 years. Some of the topics were already tackled in the past and I already forget it. The subject is also difficult to me because I did not undergo Senior high school curriculum. (P1, A11)

“Ummm, you know sir my experiences in learning English language is that I can't easily catch up those words that are new to me. I did a lot of ways to improve my fluency.” You know Sir, my experiences in learning English language is that I cannot easily catch up those words that are new to me. I did a lot of efforts to improve my fluency. (P2, A2)

Participants shared that they had experienced difficulty in understanding English words. Adult learner did a lot of ways to improve speaking skills and to become fluent in using English language. Every person has a different approach to learning another language and improving their skill in it. Adult learners developed a situational motivation in studying English. Situational interest is an emotional component especially if it involves intense concentration triggered by environmental stimuli (e.g., the desire to learn more) (Knogler et al., 2015). Situational interest may not last unless it is sustained and cultivated towards a more stable compounding interest.

Moreover, participants 4 and 5 narrated that:

“The subject matter is difficult to me, ummm, because I am a slow-learner. Hindi ko masyado maintindihan ang mga discussion or can’t catch up the lesson quickly. I can speak English language but most of the time mali ang grammar ko.” The subject matter is difficult to me because I am a slow-learner. I cannot understand and catch up lesson quickly. I can speak English language, but most of the time ungrammatical. (P5,A11)

“At my age, my experiences of learning the English language was challenging. I have difficulty in learning English language especially nowadays that English is taught via online class. Ah,,, there is no enough... time to practice and use English language.” At my age, my experiences of learning English language were challenging. I have difficulty in learning English language especially nowadays that English is taught via online class. There is no enough time to practice and use English language. (P4, A11)

Learning a second language has never been easier. Learning English as a second language is challenging and difficult, especially for adult learners.

Challenges and difficulties in learning the subject can be the result of lack of motivation, lack of self-confidence, lack of concentration and direction, poor time management, and a deadlock in the comfort zone. Challenges are difficult or impossible to overcome, and difficulties are difficult to achieve. Learning English is difficult due to the various situations that adult learners experience when learning a second language.

Kormos (2020) correctly asserts that there is indeed a pressing need for us to research and analyze the problems that twenty-first-century second language learners faced in language learning. He asserts that, while the implications of foreign language learning have indeed been carefully and exhaustively investigated to far, there are still gray areas where language learners' requirements and language teaching style must be re-evaluated.

Moreover, there are some very special learning challenges that must be acknowledged in order to establish an all-encompassing language learning environment by launching any successful language learning program in real-life circumstances (Al-Nasser, 2015). Learning processes were indeed conjectured different ways in different educational and academic environments, according to numerous investigators (Azar & Tanggaraju,2020).

Further, English language learning challenges can be personal; they can sometimes be widespread and similar, but the key to overcoming them is to understand the language learners' strengths and weaknesses, as well as their attitudes toward second language acquisition. Individual 's cognitive characteristics play a role in English language learning issues (Pfenninger & Singleton, 2016), which is why the present investigation influenced by personal English language learners, including learning difficulties and needs, as well as their thoughts about their deficiencies.

Linguistic Generalization

The phenomenon is the experiences of the Adult English language learners in their classroom communication. There are factors that affect the learning of the adult English language learners in their classroom communications in terms of personal factors, peer factors, subject matter factors and teacher factors which are reflected to their shared experiences. Thus, the findings of this study were encapsulated into a linguistic notion that illuminates the experiences of the adult English language learners in their classroom communication in four different factors. The notion is demonstrated in a schematic diagram which signified the relationship of the concept captured in the study. The notion comes in a cyclical form showing the continuous connections of the concepts.

Figure 1. Schematic Diagram of Adult English Language Learners in English Language Learning in the Classroom Communication (Abdillah, 2022)

The figure above illustrated the experiences of the adult English language learners in the classroom communication. Adult learners had experiences different factors which affect their language learning. As reflected, there are four factors on adult English language learning which are the personal factors, teacher factors, peer factors, and the subject matter factors.

The first factor is the personal factor. This factor revealed different sub-factors that affect adult English language learners in learning English in the classroom communication which included the age is not important in learning the language, English language is interesting, anxiety affects English language learning, and English language is not easy to learn.

The second is the teacher factor. In this factor on adult English language learning, it exposed different factors which affect the learning of the adult learners which included the teaching strategy and style of the teachers matter, teachers' attitudes affect learning, teacher-student age gap affect learning and teachers' command of the English language is relevant.

The third factor is the peer factor. There are identified factors on the experiences of adult learners in terms of peer factor which included the adopting to the group, peers encouragement is important, peer learning and guidance play a vital role, and past experiences and misunderstanding affect the learners.

The last one is the subject matter factors which revealed also different factors which included English as a factor for future endeavors, complexity of the subject matter, the learners' interest affect learning of the subject matter, the difficulty of the subject matter depends on the learners' perceptions.

These factors on the Adult English language learning in the classroom communication play a huge part on the adult learners. Adult English language learners had experienced these internal and external factors which affected their second language learning. Hence, this representation exposed different factors that might be a big help to the adult learners to be motivated and to be able to learn English language as second language in their classroom communication.

Further, the circles surrounded on the center of the figure represent the different factors involved in learning and influencing the adult English language learners in learning English language in the classroom communication which included the personal factors, peer factors, teacher factors, and the subject matter factors and the lines connected to these circles shows connection to each factors. The circle at the center represents the adult English language learners in their classroom communication.

Conclusions

Based on the summary of the findings, it was concluded that the interest of adult English language learners in learning English arose from their personal motivation to do so. One of the personal factors identified in this study is age is not important in language learning. This study also revealed that English language is interesting, anxiety affects English language learning, and English language is not easy to learn. Teacher factors revealed that the teacher strategy and styles matter, teachers' attitudes affect learning, teacher-student age gap affect learning, and teachers' command of the English language is relevant. The strategies, attitudes, command, and fluency of the teachers were all factors in learning English.

Moreover, it is also concluded that participants related their experiences with younger students, which demonstrated, adopting to the group, peer encouragement is important, peer learning and guidance play a vital role, and past experiences and misunderstanding affect learners. Adult learners discussed issues and concerns with their peers. Adult learners were enabled to acquire English by peer motivation and peer learning. Adult learners were challenged to communicate with younger learners due to feelings of belonging and misunderstanding among peers. Furthermore, English as factor for future endeavors, complexity of the subject matter, learners' interest affect leaning of the subject matter, and the difficulty of the subject matter depend on the learners' perceptions were all factors that participants experienced in terms of subject matter. The majority of the participants struggled with word recognition and correct usage due to the complexity of the subject. It is also revealed that English language is important for the future of adult learners to even want to learn it.

To finally conclude, the accounts of Adult English language learners in their classroom communication had been affected by the four factors which were personal factors, peer factors, teacher factors, and subject matter factors leading to challenges in learning second language in the classroom communication.

Based on the finding and conclusions of the study, the following are recommended:

The Ministry of Basic, Higher and Technical Education may provide language seminar to the teachers and adult learners to improve their language proficiency.

Adult learners should actively participate in any activities related to English language learning to improve their language proficiency.

Young learners may also initiate activities for adult learners so that they could feel comfortable in learning English language.

The language teachers may establish a strong support system, encourage, and motivate adult English language learners to learn and use English language as a medium of communication in the classroom.

The Gani L. Abpi College Inc. administrators may create programs and activities that will provide opportunities for adult English

language learners to enhance their English language fluency and proficiency.

Other researchers may look into other similar study among adult English language learners specially the affect of new curriculum in language acquisition among adult learners.

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